

Pharmacogenes associated with adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotic drugs: A systematic review

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Abstract

Pharmacogenes are specific genes that determine how an individual will respond to medication. Some of these genes have been linked to adverse reactions caused by second-generation antipsychotics. A literature search was conducted using relevant terms across the PubMed, CTG Studies, and Scopus databases. The included articles examined pharmacogenes associated with adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotics. The articles were published between 2015 and 2025. A total of 12 observational studies were included. The review protocol is registered in PROSPERO (CRD420251035803). The studies demonstrated an association of *CYP1A2* with adverse reactions induced by aripiprazole ($p < 0.035$), clozapine ($p = 0.009$, $p = 0.042$, and $p = 0.046$), and olanzapine ($p < 0.05$). *CYP2C19* was associated with clozapine-induced metabolic syndrome ($p < 0.01$). *CYP3A4* was associated with clozapine-induced hyperglycemia ($\chi^2 = 0.1$), and *CYP3A5* was associated with quetiapine ($p < 0.007$). *CYP2D6* was linked to adverse reactions induced by clozapine ($p = 0.039$), olanzapine ($p = 0.047$), risperidone ($p = 0.021$ and $p = 0.02$), and quetiapine ($p = 0.003$). This review shows that certain allelic variants of pharmacogenes are associated with adverse reactions to second-generation antipsychotics. This finding applies to patients with impaired metabolism. We recommend conducting longitudinal multicenter studies before promoting allelic variants of pharmacogenes as predictive biomarkers.

Keywords

biomarkers, pharmacogenes, poor metabolizers, schizophrenia, second-generation antipsychotics, adverse drug reactions

Introduction

Schizophrenia is a serious disorder with a complex etiology and pathogenesis. It can develop as a result of a combination of genetic, psychosocial, and environmental factors (Rybakowski 2021; Fiorillo and Giordano 2022). It is one of the top 10 causes of disability in developed countries, and more than 30% of patients are potentially suicidal, and of these, 5% commit suicide, particularly young patients (Delphin et al. 2024). The prevalence rate ranges from 0.32% (Charlson et al. 2018; Stein et al. 2022) to 1% worldwide (Marder and Cannon 2019; Delphin et al. 2024), with estimates suggesting that this mental disorder affects more than 24 million people (Charlson et al. 2018; Stein et al. 2022). In addition, these patients suffer from comorbidities with a prevalence of 25% for personality disorders (Wang et al. 2021), 45% for anxiety disorders (Kiran and Chaudhury 2016), and 70% for substance use disorders (Tekin Uludağ and Güleç 2016). Moreover, patients with schizophrenia are at higher risk of developing cardiovascular disease, diabetes, obesity, and cancer, reducing life expectancy by 15–20 years compared to the general population (Correll et al. 2022). There is also evidence that patients with schizophrenia treated with antipsychotic medications have lower mortality rates compared with untreated patients (Kim et al. 2021; Correll et al. 2022).

To reduce or control schizophrenia symptoms, first-generation “typical” antipsychotics can be used, including phenothiazines (chlorpromazine, trifluoperazine, perphenazine, prochlorperazine, acetophenazine, triflupromazine, mesoridazine), butyrophenones (haloperidol), thioxanthenes (thiothixene, chlorprothixene), dibenzoxazepines (loxapine), dihydroindoles (molindone), and diphenylbutylpiperidines (pimozide) (Drummond et al. 2018; Edinoff et al. 2022). However, second-generation antipsychotics (SGAs) are more frequently used, including clozapine, amisulpride, aripiprazole, asenapine, brexpiprazole, cariprazine, iloperidone, lurasidone, olanzapine, paliperidone, quetiapine, risperidone, sertindole, ziprasidone, and zotepine (Rognoni et al. 2021; Alvarado et al. 2025a). These drugs are not free from adverse drug reactions (ADRs), the most frequently reported being extrapyramidal symptoms (at lower incidence and severity than typical antipsychotics), dizziness, anxiety, sedation, somnolence, restlessness, weight gain, increased appetite, development of metabolic syndrome, orthostatic hypotension, and QTc prolongation (Friedrich et al. 2020; Miller and McCall 2022; Zhou et al. 2025).

Pharmacogenes are genes that can affect the absorption, distribution, metabolism, or excretion of drugs or interact with drug receptors. These genes have different allelic variants, and their combinations constitute specific genotypes that predict metabolic phenotypes classified as normal metabolizers (NM), intermediate metabolizers (IM), poor metabolizers (PM), and rapid metabolizers (RM). In IM and PM individuals, drug metabolism is reduced, leading to elevated plasma drug levels that may exceed the minimum toxic concentration and induce adverse drug reactions. Conversely, in

RM individuals, accelerated metabolism prevents the drug from reaching the minimum effective plasma concentration, which is one of the factors contributing to therapeutic failure (Alvarado et al. 2021; Alvarado et al. 2022).

Among the most relevant pharmacogenes is *CYP2D6* (22q13.2). Its wild-type allele, *CYP2D6*1*, in the homozygous genotype *CYP2D6*1/*1*, predicts NM (Ur Rasheed et al. 2017). Genotypes such as *CYP2D6*1/*9*, *CYP2D6*1/*17*, *CYP2D6*10/*10*, *CYP2D6*6/*29*, and *CYP2D6*1/*41* predict IM, while genotypes such as *CYP2D6*3/*3*, *CYP2D6*3/*4*, *CYP2D6*4/*4*, *CYP2D6*4/*5*, and *CYP2D6*6/*6* predict PM (Alvarado et al. 2021; Alvarado et al. 2023; Alvarado et al. 2025a). Another relevant gene is *CYP1A2* (15q24.1). Its wild-type allele, *CYP1A2*1A*, in the homozygous genotype *CYP1A2*1A*1A*, predicts NM, whereas the *CYP1A2*1C/*1C* genotype predicts PM (Forster et al. 2021). The *CYP2C9* gene (10q24) carries the wild-type allele *CYP2C9*1*, and in the homozygous state, the *CYP2C9*1/*1* genotype predicts NM (Karnes et al. 2021; Alvarado et al. 2025b). *CYP2C9*1/*2*, *CYP2C9*2/*2*, and *CYP2C9*1/*3* genotypes predict IM, while *CYP2C9*2/*3* and *CYP2C9*3/*3* genotypes predict PM (Alvarado et al. 2019; de Andrés et al. 2021). The *CYP2C19* gene (10q24.1) also carries the wild-type allele *CYP2C19*1*, with the *CYP2C19*1/*1* genotype predicting NM. The *CYP2C19*1/*2* genotype predicts IM, whereas *CYP2C19*2/*2*, *CYP2C19*2/*3*, and *CYP2C19*3/*3* genotypes predict PM (de Andrés et al. 2021; Alvarado et al. 2025b). The *CYP3A4* gene (7q22.1) carries the wild-type allele *CYP3A4*1.002* (commonly referred to as *CYP3A4*1A*), and the *CYP3A4*1/*1* genotype predicts NM (Wielandt et al. 2022; Musyoka et al. 2024). Conversely, the *CYP3A4*20/*20* and *CYP3A4*22/*22* genotypes predict PM (Apellániz-Ruiz et al. 2015; Zhou et al. 2017). These genes encode enzymes responsible for metabolizing several SGAs. Specifically, aripiprazole is metabolized by *CYP3A4* and *CYP2D6*; clozapine by *CYP1A2*, *CYP3A4*, *CYP3A5*, *CYP2D6*, *CYP2C19*, and *CYP2C8* (Hiemke et al. 2018; Kappel et al. 2024); olanzapine by *CYP1A2*, *CYP2D6*, *CYP3A4*, and *CYP2C9* (Kolli et al. 2023); risperidone by *CYP2D6*, *CYP3A4*, and *CYP3A5* (Soria-Chacartegui et al. 2021); paliperidone by *CYP3A4* and *CYP2D6* (Kanu et al. 2024); and quetiapine by *CYP3A4*, *CYP2D6*, *CYP2C9*, *CYP2C19*, *CYP1A2*, and *CYP3A5* (Kim et al. 2016; Zubiaur et al. 2021; Alvarado et al. 2025a).

For these reasons, it is worthwhile to apply the 4P medicine model as a new approach to medical care in schizophrenia. This model includes predictive medicine, which seeks to identify genetic and non-genetic factors that predispose individuals to disease before it manifests; preventive medicine, which enables the design of strategies to prevent disease development; personalized medicine, which tailors treatment to the individual's unique characteristics; and participatory medicine, which emphasizes shared decision-making among the patient, attending physician, biochemist, pharmacist, nurse, psychologist, and other health professionals (Alonso et al. 2019; Slim et al. 2021; Alvarado et al. 2025c).

Personalized medicine seeks to individualize the dose from the beginning of treatment by considering the genotype and phenotype profile according to ethnicity, admixture, origin, sex, and lifestyle. The purpose is to maintain plasma levels within the therapeutic range, minimizing adverse drug reactions and ensuring drug efficacy (Alvarado et al. 2019; Alvarado et al. 2023). Therefore, the objective was to review the current scientific literature on pharmacogenes associated with adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotic drugs. We analyzed the data to determine clinical implications and identify areas for future research. This review will add to the growing body of scientific evidence that supports the implementation of personalized medicine in the field of psychiatry in Peru.

Methods

A retrospective and descriptive investigation was conducted, corresponding to a systematic review of observational studies. The review was performed following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Page et al. 2021). The protocol was registered in PROSPERO (<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/view/CRD420251035803>) under registration number CRD420251035803. Cross-sectional, longitudinal, and cohort observational studies conducted in adults (≥ 18 years) that evaluated associations between pharmacogenes and adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotic drugs were included.

The evaluation of adverse reactions focused on their relationship with relevant allelic variants such as *CYP2D6*, *CYP1A2*, *CYP2C9*, *CYP2C19*, and *CYP3A4*. Studies focused on topics other than pharmacogenes and SGAs, animal research, narrative reviews, systematic and meta-analytic reviews, letters, editorials, commentaries, conference abstracts, and expert opinions were excluded.

Search strategy

A search for scientific evidence was conducted in three electronic databases: PubMed, CTG-Studies, and Scopus. The search was then optimized using keywords including “clozapine,” “olanzapine,” “risperidone,” “paliperidone,” “quetiapine,” “*CYP2D6*,” “*CYP1A2*,” “*CYP2C9*,” “*CYP2C19*,” and “*CYP3A4*” in combination with “allelic variants,” “single nucleotide polymorphism,” “pharmacogenes associated with adverse reactions,” and “adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotic drugs.”

The search results were restricted to the last 10 years, so only publications from 2015 to 10 September 2025 were retrieved. The review included articles focused on allelic variants of *CYP2D6*, *CYP1A2*, *CYP2C9*, *CYP2C19*, and *CYP3A4* as genetic biomarkers of adverse drug reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotic drugs. All studies with themes other than pharmacogenes associated with adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotic drugs were excluded.

Eligibility criteria

The research question (P.I.C.O.) was defined according to its elements (Table 1), which were: In patients with schizophrenia, are pharmacogenes encoding metabolizing enzymes associated with adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotic drugs compared with patients without single nucleotide polymorphisms?

Study article selection

The PRISMA flow diagram was used to describe the four stages of the review (Fig. 1). The articles retrieved from the search were imported into Rayyan® QCRI (<https://rayyan.qcri.org/welcome>) (Ouzzani et al. 2016). Duplicates and articles with unrelated themes were then excluded to narrow the results. Two independent reviewers (EAAV and ATA) screened and selected the articles. Each reviewer read the title, keywords, and abstract to determine whether the article was suitable for inclusion in this review. In case of disagreement, a discussion was initiated to reach consensus, and when necessary, the decision was resolved with the opinion of a third reviewer (AEMI). After the initial screening, CAAV, MSB, JAG, MRB, JJPJ, HCH, DLA, EJMM, PACG, PEYC, RPLL, WSG, AEMI, and MBA independently assessed the full text of the eligible articles to reach the final selection.

Qualitative analysis and data extraction

Data extraction was independently performed by two reviewers (EAAV and ATA) to minimize errors in data collection. The extracted information included the title, author, year, study design, sample or population, gene allelic variants, type of drug, risk of association with adverse drug reactions, conclusion, and clinical relevance (Table 2).

The articles with allelic variants associated with adverse drug reactions induced by SGAs were included based on statistical association results such as the Wald

Table 1. Protocol and content of the research question.

P.I.C.O. Elements	Outcomes
(P) Population	Adult patients of both sexes with schizophrenia carrying single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) of null or reduced function, treated with second-generation antipsychotics (clozapine, olanzapine, risperidone, paliperidone, and quetiapine).
(I) Intervention	Evaluation of SNPs in pharmacogenes (<i>CYP2D6</i> , <i>CYP1A2</i> , <i>CYP2C9</i> , <i>CYP2C19</i> , <i>CYP3A4</i>) in poor metabolizer patients associated with adverse drug reactions (ADRs) induced by second-generation antipsychotics.
(C) Comparison	Patients without SNPs in pharmacogenes <i>CYP2D6</i> , <i>CYP1A2</i> , <i>CYP2C9</i> , <i>CYP2C19</i> , and <i>CYP3A4</i> , classified as normal metabolizers, with no or minimal ADRs induced by second-generation antipsychotics.
(O) Outcomes	Pharmacogenes <i>CYP2D6</i> , <i>CYP1A2</i> , <i>CYP2C9</i> , <i>CYP2C19</i> , and <i>CYP3A4</i> are associated with ADRs induced by second-generation antipsychotics.

Figure 1. Flow chart of systematic review results.

Table 2. Variables considered in data extraction for the qualitative analysis of the studies.

Variable	Context
Title	Specific to the development of the review study.
Authors	All authors who participated in the research.
Corresponding/Lead author	Main author and study leader.
Year	Year in which the research article was published.
Study design	Types of study included in the review.
Sample or population	Target group of the study.
Allelic variants	Allelic variants of <i>CYP2D6</i> , <i>CYP1A2</i> , <i>CYP2C9</i> , <i>CYP2C19</i> , and <i>CYP3A4</i> are associated with adverse drug reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotics.
Conclusion and clinical relevance	Summary of study results.
Journal name	Journal from which the article was retrieved.
Journal relevance variables	JIF: Journal Impact Factor, Scopus indexing, and Quartile (Q).

chi-square test (χ^2), Bonferroni correction for adjusted probability values (p), Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ), and a p -value < 0.05 .

Result

A total of 776 titles and abstracts from PubMed, 48 from CTG-Studies, and 217 from Scopus, totaling 1,041 articles, were identified. After removing 277 duplicates, 855 articles proceeded to the title and abstract screening phase. During the first screening stage, 778 articles were excluded based on title and abstract alone. Seventy-seven

articles were assessed for eligibility, of which ($n = 14$) were excluded due to the absence of associations between pharmacogenes and SGA-induced adverse reactions, ($n = 18$) were limited to abstracts without full-text availability, and ($n = 33$) reported results without statistical association measures. In the second screening stage (full-text review), we included 12 studies that met the eligibility criteria, consisting of one randomized clinical trial (Koller et al. 2021), one clinical study (Zubiaur et al. 2021), and 10 observational studies: seven cross-sectional (Vandenberghe et al. 2015; Vasudev et al. 2017; Menús et al. 2020; Just et al. 2021; Ortega-Vázquez et al. 2021; Solhaug et al. 2023; Bondrescu et al. 2024), one longitudinal (Kappel et al.

2024), and two cohort studies (Ivanova et al. 2016; Costa-Dookhan et al. 2021). The PRISMA flow diagram of the literature search process is shown in Fig. 1.

Study characteristics

Observational studies

A randomized, crossover clinical trial involving 24 healthy volunteers with the *CYP1A2* genotype received aripiprazole and olanzapine doses that induced adverse drug reactions (Koller et al. 2021). A bioequivalence clinical study with 49 healthy volunteers genotyped 80 variants across 19 pharmacogenes (Zubiaur et al. 2021).

Longitudinal and cross-sectional observational studies

A longitudinal study of 6,585 pharmacokinetic assays investigated genetic variants and the metabolic pathway of clozapine (Kappel et al. 2024). In addition, seven cross-sectional observational studies focused on patients with *CYP1A2*, *CYP3A4*, and *CYP2D6* genotypes receiving clozapine, risperidone, and quetiapine, which were associated with ADRs (Vandenbergh et al. 2015; Vasudev et al. 2017; Menús et al. 2020; Just et al. 2021; Ortega-Vázquez et al. 2021; Solhaug et al. 2023; Bondrescu et al. 2024).

Observational cohort study

Two cohort studies investigated patients treated with second-generation antipsychotics, identifying allelic variants associated with adverse reactions, each with a different number of participants (Ivanova et al. 2016; Costa-Dookhan et al. 2021). The detailed characteristics of each study are presented in Table 3.

Discussion

This review shows that allelic variants of pharmacogenes are associated with adverse reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotics compared with carriers of wild-type alleles. Specifically, allelic variants such as *CYP1A2*1C*, *CYP1A2*1F*, and *CYP1A2*1B* and their respective genotypes are linked to ADRs (somnolence, headache, insomnia, dizziness, restlessness, palpitations, akathisia, and nausea) induced by aripiprazole. In the case of olanzapine, the associated ADRs include somnolence, dizziness, asthenia, constipation, dry mouth, headache, and nausea (Koller et al. 2021). Additionally, carriers of *CYP1A2*1C* experienced clozapine-induced ADRs, including sedation (62.5%), somnolence (56.25%), difficulty concentrating (54.17%), and weight gain (54.17%) (Ortega-Vázquez et al. 2021). Another study found that *CYP1A2* is associated with high plasma levels of clozapine and its metabolite N-desmethylclozapine (NDMC/norclozapine), which can induce insulin resistance in patients with schizophrenia and obesity (Costa-Dookhan et al. 2021).

Other allelic variants, such as *CYP3A4*22* (Menús et al. 2020) and *CYP2C19*2*, were linked to metabolic syndrome

(52.5%), obesity (51%), and being overweight (30.5%), dependent on elevated plasma clozapine levels (Vasudev et al. 2017; Menús et al. 2020). *CYP3A5* was related to nausea, vomiting, headache, hypotension, arrhythmias, and tachycardia induced by quetiapine (Zubiaur et al. 2021). Likewise, *CYP1A2*1F* and *CYP2D6*4* were associated with tardive dyskinesia (TD) (Ivanova et al. 2016), while *CYP2D63*, *CYP2D64*, and *CYP2D6*6* were linked to anticholinergic ADRs due to elevated plasma levels of quetiapine and norquetiapine (NDQ) (Solhaug et al. 2023). Additionally, ADRs induced by quetiapine and risperidone included dizziness (12.7%), syncope (6.2%), headache (3.9%), confusion (1.4%), seizures (1.3%), and paresthesias (1.3%) (Just et al. 2021), as well as tremors and akathisia induced by risperidone (Vandenbergh et al. 2015).

In real-world clinical practice, the use of SGAs is generally safe for most schizophrenia patients who are normal metabolizers (NMs). However, intermediate metabolizers (IMs) and poor metabolizers (PMs) face an increased risk of ADRs and even toxicity during long-term pharmacological therapy, which may impact treatment adherence. Therefore, in PM patients, personalized medicine should be implemented, with pharmacogenetic testing recommended to identify allelic variants of *CYP2D6*, *CYP1A2*, *CYP2C9*, *CYP2C19*, and *CYP3A4*. Based on these findings, pharmacological therapy should start with a personalized dosage and include therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM). Identifying metabolic genotypes/phenotypes allows for maintaining plasma levels within the therapeutic range, minimizing ADRs, and optimizing drug efficacy (Kappel et al. 2024). For identifying allelic variants of pharmacogenes, pharmacogenetic testing should be standardized and performed according to the guidelines from clinical pharmacogenetic recommendations (Bousman and Hopwood 2016; Hernandez et al. 2024). The Clinical Pharmacogenetics Implementation Consortium (CPIC) and the Dutch Pharmacogenetics Working Group (DPWG) have detailed the pharmacogenetic biomarkers and pharmacokinetic aspects underlying dose adjustments for antipsychotics and antidepressants and have provided recommendations for pharmacogenetic report preparation (Hicks et al. 2016; Bousman et al. 2023).

This study has limitations. First, most observational cross-sectional studies were conducted with small samples ($n = 48-150$). Second, the limited number of samples can generate false associations or non-associations in the statistical analysis. These limitations could cause confusion and affect the outcome. Without prejudice to the foregoing, these findings could be relevant for psychiatrists who should consider the information described before prescribing SGAs as part of the 4P medicine (predictive, preventive, personalized, and participatory). In addition, these findings constitute scientific evidence for designing future research. For pharmacists and other healthcare professionals, it could be a useful tool for performing pharmacotherapeutic monitoring and active pharmacovigilance, with the aim of predicting and detecting early adverse drug reactions of SGAs in patients with schizophrenia carrier genotypes that predict poor metabolic phenotypes.

Table 3. Pharmacogenetic studies associated with adverse drug reactions induced by second-generation antipsychotics.

Reference	Study design	Number of patients	Drug	CYP allelic variants	ADRs associated with the CYP allele and induced by SGAs	Conclusions and clinical relevance
Koller et al. (2021)	Randomized clinical trial	24	ARI OLA	<i>CYP1A2</i>	The number of recorded ADRs induced by ARI was significantly higher than that of OLA (91 vs. 60; $p < 0.035$). Psychiatric and cardiac ADRs were higher with ARI compared to OLA ($p < 0.001$).	<i>CYP1A2</i> is associated with ARI- and OLA-induced ADRs. Polymorphisms could explain the difference in the incidence of ADRs between patients.
Zubiaur et al. (2021)	Clinical trial	72	QUE	<i>CYP3A5</i>	In poor metabolizers for <i>CYP3A5</i> , the half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of QUE increases ($p < 0.007$).	Quetiapine metabolizes into DOHQE.
Kappel et al. (2024)	Observational study	6,585	CLZ	<i>CYP1A2</i>	An association was observed between <i>CYP1A2</i> and elevated plasma levels of CLZ ($\beta = 0.324$, SE = 0.124, $p = 0.009$).	The <i>CYP1A2</i> variant predicts high clozapine levels. This variant may be a genetic predictor.
Vasudev et al. (2017)	Observational study	60	CLZ	<i>CYP2C19*2</i>	<i>CYP2C19*2/LEPR</i> are associated with metabolic syndrome (MS) induced by elevated CLZ levels compared with patients without MS (CLZ 1886 ± 895 vs. 1283 ± 985 ng/mL, $p < 0.01$).	<i>CYP2C19</i> and <i>LEPR</i> may be predictive biomarkers of MS.
Menus et al. (2020)	Observational study	96	CLZ	<i>CYP3A4*1B</i> <i>CYP3A4*22</i> <i>CYP3A5*3</i>	<i>CYP3A4</i> is associated with high plasma levels of CLZ inducing hyperglycemia ($\chi^2 = 0.1$, $n = 87$, $p = 0.98$) compared with patients with therapeutic CLZ concentrations (OR = 11.8; 95% CI 1.9–71.9).	Poor metabolizers <i>CYP3A4</i> has elevated plasma levels of clozapine, glucose, and a higher body mass index (BMI).
Ortega-Vázquez et al. (2021)	Observational study	48	CLZ	<i>CYP2D6*10</i> <i>CYP2D6*1C</i> <i>CYP2D6*1D</i>	<i>CYP2D6*10/*10</i> ($p = 0.039$) is associated with CLZ-induced neurological ADRs. <i>CYP1A2*1C</i> and <i>CYP1A2*1D</i> are associated with CLZ-induced ADRs ($p = 0.042$ and $p = 0.046$, respectively).	<i>CYP1A2*1C</i> and <i>CYP2D6*10</i> variants would be potential biomarkers to predict clozapine-induced ADRs in patients with refractory psychosis and concomitant alcohol intake.
Vandenberghé et al. (2015)	Observational study	150	RSP	<i>CYP2D6*3</i> <i>CYP2D6*4</i>	<i>CYP2D6</i> PMs had 28% higher AUC, high RSP plasma inducing tremor, and akathisia ($p = 0.01$ and $p = 0.02$, respectively).	Therapeutic drug monitoring is recommended to adjust the dose, with the goal of maintaining plasma RSP levels within the therapeutic window (20–40 ng/mL), which is associated with a lower risk of ADR.
Just et al. (2021)	Observational study	2939	QUE RSP	<i>CYP2D6</i>	A relationship was observed between <i>CYP2D6</i> and ADRs (headache, dizziness, and dyskinesia) induced by QUE ($p = 0.70$) and RSP ($p = 0.196$) compared to those without this effect.	A non-functional <i>CYP2D6</i> allele was shown to be associated with quetiapine-induced dizziness.
Solhaug et al. (2023)	Observational study	14613	QUE	<i>CYP2D6*3</i> <i>CYP2D6*4</i> <i>CYP2D6*6</i> <i>CYP2D6*9</i> <i>CYP2D6*10</i>	Reduction in the C:D ratio of QUE (–16%, $p = 0.05$) in PM compared to NM. The C:D ratios of NDQ were significantly higher in IM (NDQ: +8%, $p = 0.001$) and PM (NDQ: +15%, $p = 0.003$) compared to NM.	<i>CYP2D6</i> IM and PM patients showed higher plasma levels of norquetiapine (NDQ) compared to NM. This could affect both the tolerability and efficacy of QUE treatment.
Bondrescu et al. (2024)	Observational study	107	RSP	<i>CYP2D6*4</i>	A correlation was found between <i>CYP2D6*4</i> and the occurrence of RSP-induced tremors and rigidity ($p = 0.23$; $p = 0.021$).	The significant association between <i>CYP2D6*4</i> and an increased risk of risperidone-induced ADR in monotherapy could affect treatment adherence in poor metabolizers.
Ivanova et al. (2016)	Cohort	475	OLA	<i>CYP1A2*1F</i> <i>CYP2D6*4</i>	The <i>CYP1A2*1F</i> frequency was 1.3 times higher in patients with tardive dyskinesia (TD) than in those without TD ($\chi^2 = 4.65$, $p < 0.05$). <i>CYP2D6*4</i> carriers (G > A) are associated with elevated plasma levels of TD-inducing OLA compared to (A/A) ($\chi^2 = 5.25$, $p = 0.047$).	Carriers of <i>CYP1A2*1F</i> and <i>CYP2D6*4</i> present elevated plasma levels of OLA that induce tardive dyskinesia.
Costa-Dookhan et al. (2021)	Cohort	38	CLZ	<i>CYP1A2</i>	Inverse association between CLZ/NDMC ratio and HOMA-IR ($\beta = -1.028$, SE $\beta = 0.473$, $\beta = -0.348$, $p = 0.037$). CLZ/NDMC and fasting serum insulin ($\beta = -27.124$, SE = 12.081, $\beta = -0.351$, $p = 0.031$).	Elevated CLZ: NDMC in plasma may predict insulin resistance in patients with schizophrenia and obesity.

ADRs: adverse drug reactions; SGAs: second-generation antipsychotics; LEPR: leptin receptor; ARI: aripiprazole; CLZ: clozapine; OLA: olanzapine; RSP: risperidone; WHAT: quetiapine; DHARI: dehydroaripiprazole; NDMC: N-desmethylclozapine; NDQ: norquetiapine; DOHQE: 7.8-dihydroxyquetiapine; HOMA-IR: Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance; SE: beta standard error; χ^2 : Wald chi-square test; Rho: Spearman's correlation coefficient (p); C:D concentration: dose ratio; OR: odds ratio; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval.

Conclusion

The reviewed articles demonstrate a correlation between certain allelic variants (*CYP1A2*1C*, *CYP1A2*1F*, *CYP1A2*1B*, *CYP3A4*22*, *CYP2C19*2*, *CYP2D6*3*, *CYP2D6*4*, and *CYP2D6*6*) and adverse reactions to second-generation antipsychotics in patients with impaired metabolism. We recommend longitudinal multicenter

pharmacogenetic studies before promoting the allelic variants as predictive biomarkers.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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